

FINAL REPORT

1 General information

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2 Summary

In a collaboration between TU Dresden and the Institute for Radiation Physics at HZDR, advancements in porosimetry for MOFs were explored. The study combined PALS with physical and chemical methods to improve the understanding of physisorption mechanisms of gases and vapors in environmentally relevant and chemically stable MOFs. In situ PALS was used to study phase transitions in MOFs, induced by temperature or guest molecules. This approach helped to decouple pore transitions and pore filling in switchable MOFs and identify residual closed porosity and defects.

The interaction between positronium (Ps) and metal ions challenges PALS porosimetry, particularly in open-metal-site MOFs like CPO-27 (M). Diamagnetic Mg^{2+} promotes oxidation while maintaining longer lifetimes, whereas paramagnetic Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} inhibit and quench o-Ps through spin conversion, and oxidation, leading to shorter lifetimes. In situ gas adsorption experiments by PALS showed that only O_2 reduced quenching, bringing lifetimes closer to expected values. These findings emphasize the strong influence of metal ions on the Ps lifetime and encourage the community to introduce corrections to existing models.

PALS provided new insight into water adsorption in DUT-67 (Zr,Hf). In situ measurements revealed stepwise uptake, with DUT-67(Hf) exhibiting stronger water clustering and limiting pore filling compared to DUT-67(Zr). Similarly, PALS analysis of CALF-20 (Zn) showed selective CO_2 adsorption over H_2O at low humidity, making it promising for carbon capture. Combined PALS, PXRD, and gas adsorption data revealed a sequential CO_2 uptake mechanism, with molecules filling cage centers, forming chains, and adhering to pore walls. However, humidity disrupted CO_2 adsorption by forming hydrogen-bond networks.

PALS identified residual porosity and defects in switchable MOFs (DUT-8(Ni), MIL-53(Al), and ZIF-7). In DUT-8(Ni), mesopores were detected, most likely from missing building blocks that hinder gas diffusion. These defects may aid structural relaxation during phase transitions. MIL-53(Al) exhibited less defects, while ZIF-7 (Zn) showed an interesting phenomenon, indicating the dependency of defect amount closely related to guest-induced phase transition and temperature. MIL-53(Al) showed an expected CO_2 -induced np-lp transition at 195K, with reversible hysteresis. Ps intensity reached a minimum at the point of transition, suggesting defined changes in surface chemistry. Variable temperature experiments confirmed the switchability of the framework. In case of variable temperature CO_2 physisorption in ZIF-7(Zn), the S-shaped o-Ps intensity with CO_2 pressure suggests framework flexibility. Unlike MIL-53(Al), ZIF-7 lacked a pronounced intensity drop, likely due to higher defect concentration. These findings indicate that surface alterations during transitions are prominent in defect-free MOFs but negligible in defect-containing ones. Further studies are needed to generalize these observations.

In Zusammenarbeit mit der TU Dresden und dem Institut für Strahlenphysik am HZDR wurden neue PALS-Anwendungen für MOFs untersucht. Die Studie kombinierte PALS mit chemischen Methoden, um die Wasserdampf- und Gasadsorption in umweltrelevanten MOFs besser zu verstehen. Zudem half PALS, Porenübergänge in schaltbaren MOFs zu entkoppeln und verbleibende geschlossene Porosität sowie Defekte zu identifizieren.

Die Wechselwirkung von Positronium (Ps) mit Metallionen erschwert die PALS-Porosimetrie, besonders bei MOFs mit offenen Metallstellen wie CPO-27 (M). Während Mg^{2+} die Oxidation fördert und längere Lebensdauern erhält, löschen Co^{2+} und Ni^{2+} o-Ps durch Spinumwandlung und

Oxidation, was kürzere Lebensdauern verursacht. Gasadsorptionsexperimente zeigen, dass nur O_2 das Quenching reduziert und die Lebensdauern den erwarteten Werten annähert. Dies unterstreicht den starken Einfluss der Metallionen auf PALS und die Notwendigkeit von Korrekturen.

PALS lieferte Einblicke in die Wasseradsorption in DUT-67 (Zr,Hf). In-situ-Messungen zeigten eine schrittweise Aufnahme, wobei DUT-67 (Hf) mehr Wasser akkumulierte als DUT-67 (Zr), was die Porenfüllung begrenzte. Diese strukturellen Unterschiede beeinflussen das Wasseraufnahmevermögen in der Atmosphäre. Ebenso zeigte die PALS-Analyse von CALF-20 (Zn) eine selektive CO_2 -Adsorption bei niedriger Luftfeuchtigkeit, was es für die CO_2 -Bindung vielversprechend macht. PALS-, PXRD- und Gasadsorptionsdaten belegten einen sequentiellen CO_2 -Aufnahmemechanismus mit Käfigfüllung, Kettenbildung und Wandhaftung, wobei Feuchtigkeit die Adsorption durch Wasserstoffbrücken-Netzwerke störte.

PALS identifizierte Restporosität und Defekte in schaltbaren MOFs wie DUT-8 (Ni), MIL-53 (Al) und ZIF-7 (Zn). In DUT-8 (Ni) wurden verborgene Mesoporen entdeckt, die vermutlich durch fehlende Bausteine verursacht werden, die die Gasdiffusion behindern. Diese Defekte könnten die strukturelle Relaxation bei Phasenübergängen unterstützen. MIL-53 (Al) wies keine Defekte auf, während ZIF-7 (Zn) einen Defektyp zeigte, der in der großporigen Phase zunahm, sowie einen weiteren, der mit der Temperatur variierte.

MIL-53(Al) zeigte einen CO_2 -induzierten np-zu-1p-Übergang bei 70-100 mbar mit reversibler Hysterese. Die minimale Ps-Intensität während des Übergangs weist auf Veränderungen der Oberflächenchemie hin. Thermische Experimente bestätigten die Schaltbarkeit, aber die Intensität blieb nur während der Erwärmung nahe RT gering, was auf vorübergehende Oberflächenveränderungen hinweist. Bei ZIF-7 (Zn) variierte die o-Ps-Intensität mit dem CO_2 -Druck, was auf Flexibilität hinweist, während andere Gase keine Reaktion zeigten. Anders als bei MIL-53(Al) trat kein ausgeprägter Intensitätsabfall auf, vermutlich aufgrund von Defekten. Die Ergebnisse zeigen, dass defektfreie MOFs bei Übergängen chemische Veränderungen durchlaufen, während defekthaltige MOFs primär auf die Gasaufnahme reagieren. Weitere Studien sind nötig, um diese Beobachtungen zu verallgemeinern.

3 Progress Report

3.1 Research question / objectives

Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) are highly porous materials with tunable structures,^[1,2] determined by metal centers and organic linkers.^[3] Their versatility enables applications in gas adsorption, separation, drug delivery, catalysis, and electronics.^[4,5] Some MOFs exhibit switchable behavior, undergoing structural transformations in response to external stimuli like gas molecules, temperature, or pressure.^[6] Core-shell MOFs, where a MOF core^[7] is encapsulated by a second shell, offer dual functionality, enhancing stability, selectivity, and guest diffusion.

Despite their potential, characterizing switchable and core-shell MOFs remains challenging. In switchable MOFs, the nature of closed pores and defect formation during transitions is unclear, as gas adsorption induces pore opening and cannot probe transition-state defects. In core-shell MOFs, assessing depth-dependent porosity and environmental effects (e.g., humidity) is crucial for understanding guest transport.

Positron annihilation lifetime spectroscopy (PALS)^[8,9] uniquely detects all pores both accessible and inaccessible for gas molecules, even under in situ gas adsorption conditions.^[10–12] Slow positron beams further enable depth-resolved porosity and defect analysis,^[13] making them valuable for core-shell MOFs. In porous materials, positronium (Ps) annihilates with characteristic lifetimes linked to pore properties.^[14,15] Despite its potential, PALS remains underutilized in MOF research. Notably, Ps interactions with metal nodes can alter annihilation parameters, risking misinterpretations of porosity—an aspect largely unexplored.

This project aims to (i) standardize Ps porosimetry by identifying interactions that underestimate pore sizes and (ii) integrate PALS with gas adsorption to enhance MOF characterization under in situ conditions. Key research questions include:

- 1) How does the atomic number (Z) of MOF metal nodes influence o-Ps quenching? Can we establish a Z-dependent quenching probability and propose functionalization strategies to mitigate it for accurate pore size measurements?
- 2) How can we correct for o-Ps migration from main pores to interparticle spaces in small-particle MOFs? How do pore shape, size, and connectivity influence this migration?
- 3) How can we quantify and tailor residual porosity in the closed-pore state of switchable MOFs? Does residual porosity affect switchability, such as gate opening pressure? In situ PALS measurements offer unique insights.
- 4) What is the residual porosity in core-shell MOFs? How do synthesis and desolvation impact surface degradation and shell formation? Can shell thickness be controlled? Depth profiling via slow positron beams can differentiate shell and core porosity.

We targeted some of these questions in an iterative manner. In selected cases it was challenging to synthesize suitable model systems, and we focused on critical fundamental questions. After successfully establishing basic in situ techniques, we realized the high impact for water and CO₂ adsorption applications. Given the urgent demand for efficient adsorbents for carbon dioxide capture in the presence of moisture and materials for harvesting water in arid regions, we refocused parts of our investigation. Specifically, we explored the mechanistic aspects of water adsorption in the chemically stable DUT-67 (Zn, Hf) MOFs and conducted a detailed analysis of CO₂ adsorption under ambient conditions in CALF-20 (Zn).

The project, led by Prof. Dr. Stefan Kaskel (TUD) and Dr. Ahmed Gamal Attallah Elsherif (HZDR), was divided into five work packages (WPs), conducted equally by HZDR (PALS measurements) and TU Dresden (TUD) (MOFs synthesis, characterization and in situ XRD studies). The WPs were carried out by Dr. Ahmed Gamal Attallah Elsherif (HZDR), Dr. Volodymyr Bon (TUD) and coworkers at TUD. Dr. Andreas Wagner and Dr. Eric Hirschmann supported the HZDR work. Collaborations included Dr. Radosław Zaleski (Marie Curie-Skłodowska University, Lublin, Poland) and Dr. Asier Zubiaga (Glas Trösch Group, Bützberg, Bern, Switzerland).

3.2 Achieved results and discussions

We summarize the results based on the proposed work packages. WP1 and WP2 focused on standardizing PALS in model MOFs by examining the effects of pore chemistry, particle size, and pore dimensions. WP2 was modified to include in situ water adsorption experiments in DUT-67 MOFs. Additionally, a new PALS chamber with a gas dosing system, humidity control, and gas mixing unit was built at HZDR. WP3 replaced the core-shell study with extensive in situ CO₂ uptake experiments on CALF-20. WP4 investigated defects in switchable MOFs (DUT-8 (Ni), MIL-53 (Al), and ZIF-7 (Zn)). WP5 extended WP4, analyzing stimuli-induced framework flexibility in MIL-53(Al) and ZIF-7 via in situ PALS.

3.2.1 Role of pore chemical composition on PALS data (WP1)

This section explores the often-overlooked interactions between Ps and metal ions, which contribute to contradictory interpretation of the pore size. We investigated a family of MOFs with open-metal-site (CPO-27 (M = Mg, Ni, Co)), where bare metal sites enable direct Ps-metal interactions. These materials are isostructural showing the 1D channel type pores of the same size.

Results from **P3** demonstrate that metal ions significantly impact PALS measurements, with a strong correlation between metal identity and apparent porosity. By comparing simulated o-Ps lifetimes (6.27 ns) and gas adsorption data with experimental PALS values, we identified distinct quenching mechanisms. Paramagnetic ions (Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+}) induce spin conversion and oxidation,

leading to shorter o-Ps lifetimes, while diamagnetic Mg^{2+} primarily facilitates Ps oxidation, producing unique PALS signatures. Table 1 confirms this, showing the highest τ_3 and I_3 values for Mg^{2+} , with a notable reduction in

	Mg^{2+}	Co^{2+}	Ni^{2+}
τ_3 / ns	3.94 ± 0.01	2.50 ± 0.04	2.65 ± 0.07
I_3 / %	37.49 ± 0.13	3.40 ± 0.06	2.60 ± 0.06

I_3 for paramagnetic ions Co^{2+} and Ni^{2+} . These findings highlight the complexity of o-Ps quenching in MOFs and the importance of considering metal ion chemistry for accurate PALS interpretation. More broadly, they refine our understanding of how metal ions influence Ps interactions, improving MOF porosity characterization. While Monte Carlo (MC) simulations in **P3** estimated Ps lifetimes without metal-site quenching in CPO-27, incorporating Zn-dependent and oxidation state-specific quenching remains challenging. A fully corrected model would require extensive MC parameterization. To mitigate Ps quenching, we initially proposed grafting metal-selective groups (e.g., amines, N-donors) onto metal sites but sought a more practical shielding approach without synthesis modifications. Instead, we tested CO_2 , N_2 , and O_2 adsorption to chemically saturate the metal ions (**P4**). Despite CPO-27's strong CO_2 affinity,^[16] Ps quenching persisted even at low CO_2 concentrations. Among the tested gases, only O_2 significantly reduced quenching, yielding a Ps lifetime (~6 ns) closer to the expected 6.27 ns (Figure 1). Exposing CPO-27(Mg) to 10^{-2} mbar O_2 for 30 minutes, followed by thermal cycling (90 K–400 K), likely induced MgO formation, which further reduced Ps quenching. We believe this adsorption-based approach could be highly beneficial for the scientific community, particularly in cases where pronounced Ps quenching is observed.

Figure 1. Temporal evolution of Ps lifetime and the corresponding intensity in CPO-27 (Mg) during cycling the sample between 90 K, 273 K, and 400 K.

3.2.2 Role of particle size and pore size on PALS data (WP2)

We initially outlined a study of DUT-49(Cu) to assess how particle and pore size affect Ps escape, which can underestimate Ps lifetime ($1/\tau_{\text{pore}} = 1/\tau_{\text{pore}} + 1/\tau_{\text{escape}}$). However, as Sec. 3.2.1 and **P3** highlight, Ps quenching at metal sites is found to be complex and difficult to isolate. Even if particle size effects were resolved, chemical quenching would still lead to underestimation in PALS results. We found that introducing silicon oil to open structure can damp the migration fraction. Figure 2 shows that adding silicon oil to DUT-67 (Zr) fills the interparticle voids and, due to suboptimal oil loading, shifts / fills the cavity component. Hence, we knew that a proper protocol can be adapted to selectively fill the interparticle space. However, in our studies we realized the high relevance of

water adsorption for environmental science and sustainability targeting water capture in arid areas. For this topic, we applied PALS together with vapor adsorption to understand the adsorption mechanism of water in DUT-67 (Zr,Hf) (**P2**). This study involved conducting in situ PALS measurements while exposing the samples to varying levels of relative humidity (RH).

The results in **P2** provided key insights into the sequential water uptake process in DUT-67. Water first fills the octahedral cages (up to 26% RH in Zr and 35% RH in Hf), then the middle cuboctahedral cages (35% RH in Zr and 9–50% RH in Hf), and finally the large cuboctahedral cages (43% RH in Zr vs. 50% RH in Hf). These adsorption stages are evident in Figure 3, based on Ps lifetime (panel a) and intensity (panel b) variations. PALS measurements also revealed differences in hydrophilicity, with DUT-67(Hf) exhibiting pronounced water clustering in the middle cuboctahedral cages, restricting pore filling compared to the more uniform distribution in DUT-67-Zr. The distinct behavior of Ps intensity as an index of vapor adsorption further emphasizes the potential of PALS in refining our understanding of water uptake mechanisms in microporous materials.

3.2.3 Core-shell structures in MOFs (WP3)

This part was tailored to be conducted at the slow positron beam MePS facility at the HZDR, which is a user dedicated facility that requires applying for beamtimes twice a year. Since this study involved the growth of a polymer (shell) on a MOF (core), we initially applied for beamtime in 2022 to validate and optimize the synthesis conditions for achieving a shell layer with controlled thickness. Additionally, we aimed to assess the resolvability of both shell and core layers using the slow positron beam. Our proposal was granted, allowing us to use DUT-67 (Zr and Hf) as cores due to their chemical and thermal stability and non-quenching effect on Ps. Various polymeric shells were synthesized, including methacrylate copolymer, polyphenyl-methylsiloxane, and polyvinyl butyral (PVB). Figure 4 shows o-Ps characteristics in DUT-67-Zr-PVB. Our experiments found that o-Ps lifetime could not resolve the shell layer due to the overlap with surface states. However, o-Ps intensity successfully distinguished the shell layer, estimating its thickness at ~ 45 nm. Our 2023 beamtime proposal to study thicker polymer shells

Figure 2. Pore size distribution from PALS analysis of DUT-67 (Zr) with and without silicon oil.

Figure 3. Dependence of Ps (a) lifetime and (b) intensities in different free volumes in DUT-67 (Zr & Hf) on relative humidity.

Figure 4. o-Ps lifetime and intensity in different pores in DUT-67 (Zr) with polyvinyl butyral as a top layer as a function of positron implantation energy.

and humidity-exposed core-shell structures was not granted due to overbooking. In parallel, we expanded our investigation to CO₂ adsorption under ambient conditions, focusing on CALF-20, a promising candidate with selective CO₂ adsorption over H₂O at low humidity, industrial scalability, and good CO₂/N₂ selectivity.^[17] In this study (**P5**), we systematically examined CALF-20 (Zn) under varying temperature and humidity using PALS, in situ PXRD, and gas adsorption to assess its structural and adsorption properties for carbon capture.

The observed o-Ps intensity behavior aligns well with Langmuir-Freundlich isotherms (Figure 5i), revealing that o-Ps intensity can effectively reflect the adsorption isotherm—beforehand an undocumented finding. Our results indicate that CO₂ adsorption in CALF-20 follows a sequential mechanism: molecules first occupy cage centers, then form 1D chains, and finally adhere to pore walls (Figure 5ii). PALS measurements show that the spatial arrangement of CO₂ within the cages creates temperature- and pressure-dependent gaps, influencing adsorption capacity. Figure 5ii illustrates these adsorption steps. Our investigation of humidity effects on CO₂ adsorption revealed competitive interactions within the MOF framework. At low RH, water molecules form isolated clusters with minimal hydrogen bonding, but beyond 35%, they create hydrogen-bond networks, altering pore free volumes. Under humid CO₂ conditions, competitive adsorption initially disrupts water propagation, but at high RH, water dominates, suggesting pore flexibility and structural rearrangements. These findings underscore humidity's critical role in CO₂ adsorption efficiency. This knowledge is essential for optimizing CALF-20's application in carbon capture technologies, particularly for industrial developments. This study on pure and humid gas adsorption in situ during PALS was conducted using the newly upgraded PALS chamber (**P4**), specifically designed for such investigations. Initially aimed at reducing dead volume, the setup underwent a full reconstruction, resulting in a multifunctional chamber supporting adsorption experiments under controlled pressure (10⁻⁶ mbar to 1.5 bar) and temperature (50–480 K) conditions. A key feature is its novel gas dosing system, enabling precise dosing of the gases, including CO₂, N₂, Ar, and O₂, as well as their mixtures. Additionally, an advanced humidity control system allows for detailed studies on water vapor's impact on gas adsorption mechanisms.

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Figure 5. (i) Correlation between o-ps intensity in CALF-20 cages with the amount of adsorbed CO₂ by classical gas adsorption. (ii) arrangement of CO₂ in CALF-20 as a function of CO₂ pressure as expected from o-Ps parameters.

3.2.4 Structural defects in switchable MOFs (WP4)

This work package examined residual porosity and defects in DUT-8(Ni), which influence switchability but remain poorly understood. Small-particle DUT-8 is expected to have higher defect concentrations, challenging to quantify by X-ray diffraction techniques. In (**P1**), we showed that desolvated DUT-8(Ni) transitions into a confined closed pore phase (ccp), with its initial pore state dictating the transition temperature. PALS identified solvent-inaccessible porosity in the cp phase, revealing matrix free volumes (0.52 nm), micropores (0.86 nm), and mesopores (2.43 nm). Upon transition to ccp, these values slightly increased (0.56 nm & 0.95 nm), while the size of mesopores reduced to 2.08 nm. Since crystal structure analysis shows no mesopores in either phase (**P1**), this likely stems from minor structural deformations due to missing building blocks. The information

about the defects in MOFs is of paramount importance for various potential applications, especially as heterogeneous catalysts. However, it is still challenging to quantify the number of defects in MOFs using standard characterization techniques. Some progress could be achieved by using in situ EPR and NMR spectroscopy, however, the universal technique for defect quantification in MOFs is still not established. PALS results suggest these defects facilitate structural relaxation and expansion during the cp-to-ccp transition. As o-Ps is insensitive to pore length, the increased matrix free volumes and micropores indicate widening rather than elongation, with inaccessible pores likely blocked by missing building units.

We proposed synthesizing and characterizing DUT-8 (M = Ni, Co, Zn, Cu) under varying desolvation conditions and aimed to quantify ELM-11. However, both frameworks show a large amplitude of the structural changes from completely dense phase to porous open pore phase. This process accompanied by strong strains and tensions within the crystallites resulting in the new defects after each adsorption/desorption cycle.^[18] This prompts us to select the model systems, more stable for adsorption/desorption cycles in order to exclude additional variable, namely the spatiotemporal component from the study. Therefore, we selected MIL-53(Al) and ZIF-7 frameworks for in situ PALS studies under gas loading, which are known to be stable upon adsorption/desorption cycles. MIL-53(Al) shows a classical “breathing” behavior (contraction and reopening) and ZIF-7 shows opening and closing of the structure upon physisorption of gas molecules. Figure 6 shows the longest-lived o-Ps lifetimes in both materials. In MIL-53(Al), τ_4 (15–18 ns) suggests mesopores likely due to defects. However, the absence of defects in XRD and the decent I_4 imply o-Ps moves freely in a Bloch-like state (P5). The change in τ_4 results from increased o-Ps collisions with pore walls at higher temperatures, enhancing annihilation probability, while I_4 increases with temperature as more o-Ps contribute to the Bloch state. ZIF-7 exhibits two long o-Ps lifetime components, attributed to intracrystal (defect1) and intercrystal (defect2) defects. The increase in τ_{defect1} indicates growing free volume rather than a Bloch state. Since ZIF-7 remains in the np phase up to ~100 °C and transitions to lp around 700 °C,^[19] the low initial I_{defect1} suggests minimal intracrystal defects, which increase as T approaches the lp phase. Quantification of defect1 at high T was limited by the Kapton-sealed source, but future experiments with metallic foil sources will allow revisiting this behavior. In contrast, τ_{defect2} remains constant with T, while I_{defect2} increases, indicating structural stability of intercrystal regions. Results in Figure 6 are unpublished and will appear in the WP5 publication.

Figure 6. Thermal effect on longest-lived o-Ps lifetimes in (top) MIL-53(Al) and (bottom) ZIF-7(Zn).

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3.2.5 In situ gas adsorption in switchable MOFs (WP5 - unpublished)

Figure 8 demonstrates CO₂-induced structural switchability in MIL-53(Al) via τ_3 and I_3 from PALS. In Figure 8a, τ_3 initially corresponds to the np phase at low p_{CO_2} , transitioning to lp between 70–100 mbar. Then decreasing at higher p_{CO_2} due to pore filling. The transformation is reversible, with a 30-mbar hysteresis during desorption. I_3 in Figure 8b exhibits a distinct minimum at the np-to-lp transition, likely indicating an alteration in the pore surface chemistry. Since o-Ps formation decreases with reduced surface I_3 shows hysteresis, increasing in the lp and in the fully filled phase

(>100 mbar). This rise in intensity suggests that CO₂ enhances electron density by adsorbing on the inner pore surface and closing the cavities on the pore surface, promoting Ps formation at pore surface and between adsorbed CO₂ molecules (similar to **P5**). To assess if the I₃ reduction stems from gas-induced sample compression, we examined thermal switchability under vacuum (~1.5 × 10⁻⁶ mbar, Figure 9). The np-to-1p transition is evident from T₃ (Figure 9a), with pore sizes closely matching crystallographic calculations. However, I₃ in Figure 9b remains low at the exact transformation temperature, but only during heating. This suggests that, from an o-Ps perspective, the switchability in MIL-53(Al) temporarily reduces surface area, irrespective of the switching stimuli. To compare pore behavior in switchable MOFs, we analyzed ZIF-7 under various gases (CO₂, N₂, Ar, CH₄ in Figure 7) across various Ts to assess whether reduced pore-related o-Ps intensity is a

Figure 8. Variation of o-Ps lifetime and intensity in MIL-53 (Al) with CO₂ sorption pressure at 195 K.

Figure 9. Thermal switchability of MIL-53 (Al) as resolved by PALS.

general phenomenon in flexible MOFs and its implications for gas-framework interactions and potential modifications in surface chemistry. Crystallographic calculations show ZIF-7 pores ranging from 0.3 to 0.6 nm, with o-Ps lifetimes too close to resolve individually, averaging into a single component. Figure 7 presents o-Ps intensity in aperture and cavity of ZIF-7 under different gas and temperature conditions, with lifetimes (not shown) following the same trend. Key observations from Figure 7: (i) o-Ps intensity with CO₂ shows a sigmoidal change with pressure, suggesting a structure flexibility. Fitting these curves to an adsorption isotherm (**P5**) could provide more insights. Notably, S-shape o-Ps intensity is deformed at RT indicating that cooperativity may be altered with increasing the temperature, e.g. the crystal size dependency become more pronounced (ii) other gases show nearly constant o-Ps intensity with pressure, suggesting no pore response. (iii) o-Ps intensity does not scale uniformly with temperature, peaking at 195 K in CO₂ but lower in N₂, Ar, and CH₄, indicating a gas-dependent pore surface alteration. (iv) Unlike MIL-53 (Al), CO₂-induced flexibility in ZIF-7 lacks an intensity minimum. Defect1 and defect2 (not shown) remain resolvable across all gases and T in ZIF-7(Zn), with consistently lower intensity than pore-related component (I_{ap.+lcav.}). This could suggest that defects in ZIF-7 (Zn) allow minor sur-

Figure 7. Dependence of o-Ps intensity inside aperture and cavities of ZIF-7 (Zn) as a function of in situ adsorption pressure during various gas adsorption experiments at different temperatures.

face variation, while the phase transition in Mil-53(AI) showing no mesoporosity may lead to significant changes in pore chemistry. At the moment, we are working on the explanation of these phenomena and will apply additional advanced characterization techniques for confirmation of in situ PALS data. We plan to publish the results above as a comparative study of switchable MOFs by PALS.

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4 Published Project Results

4.1 Publications with scientific quality assurance

Journal articles

- P1.** Ehrling, S.; Senkowska, I.; Efimova, A.; Bon, V.; Abylgazina, L.; Petkov, P.; Evans, J.D.; Attallah, A. Gamal; Wharmby, M.T.; Roslova, M.; Huang, Z.; Tanaka, H.; Wagner, A.; Schmidt, P.; Kaskel, S. "Temperature Driven Transformation of the Flexible Metal–Organic Framework DUT-8(Ni)", *Chem. – A Eur. J.*, Vol. 28, pp e202201281, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1002/chem.202201281>
- P2.** Attallah, A. G.; Bon, V.; Maity, K.; Hirschmann, E.; Butterling, M.; Wagner, A.; Kaskel, S. "Unravelling the Water Adsorption Mechanism in Hierarchical MOFs: Insights from In Situ Positron Annihilation Lifetime Studies", *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, Vol. 15, pp. 48264, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.3c10974>
- P3.** Attallah, A. G.; Bon, V.; Maity, K.; Zaleski, R.; Hirschmann, E.; Kaskel, S.; Wagner, A. "Revisiting Metal–Organic Frameworks Porosimetry by Positron Annihilation: Metal Ion States and Positronium Parameters", *J. Phys. Chem. Lett.*, Vol. 15, pp. 4560, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcllett.4c00762>
- P4.** Attallah, A. G.; Hirschmann, E.; Butterling, M.; Hartmann, A.; Stach, D.; Findeisen, S.; Bon, V.; Kaskel, S.; Wagner, A. "Advanced setup for in situ positron annihilation lifetime measurements under variable gas atmospheres and humidity: From cryogenic to high temperatures", *AIP Advances*, Vol. 14, pp. 105104, 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0226137>
- P5.** Attallah, A. G.; Bon, V.; Hirschmann, E.; Butterling, M.; Wagner, A.; Zaleski, R.; Kaskel, S. "Uncovering the Dynamic CO₂ Gas Uptake Behavior of CALF-20 (Zn) under Varying Conditions via Positronium Lifetime Analysis", *Small* **2025**, 2500544. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sml.202500544>

4.2 Other publications

Journal article

OP1. Nelliyl, R. B.; Mor, J.; Thota, M.; Liedke, M. O.; Butterling, M.; Attallah, A. G.; Hirschmann, E.; Wagner, A.; Sharma, S. K. "Pore-Structure Investigation of Bimetallic Zeolitic Imidazolate Framework-8 Films with Varying Co/Zn Nodes Ratio Using Depth Sensitive Positronium Annihilation Lifetime Spectroscopy", *J. Phys. Chem. C*, Vol. 128, pp. 1901, 2024.

OP1. Franke, J.; Zysk, F.; Wilski, S.; Liedke, M. O.; Butterling, M.; Attallah, A. G.; Wagner, A.; Kühne, T. D.; Dahlmann, R. "Consideration of the Effect of Nanoscale Porosity on Mass Transport Phenomena in PECVD Coatings", *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.*, Vol. 57, pp. 405303, 2024.

OP3. Rathi, A.; Bernal-Ortega, P.; Attallah, A. G.; Krause-Rehberg, R.; Elsayed, M.; Trimbach, J.; Bergmann, C.; Blume, A. "TDAE Aromatic Oil Preference for Polymer Blends: An Analysis of S-SBR, BR, and Miscible S-SBR/BR Systems" *Polymer*, Vol. 308, 127359, 2024.

Press release

PR1. How to capture water from air, Joint press release of TU Dresden and HZDR of January 5, 2024, <https://www.hzdr.de/db/Cms?pNid=99&pOid=70994>

PR2. Understanding carbon traps, Joint press release of TU Dresden, Maria-Curie-Skłodowska University Lublin and Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR) of May 13, 2025, <https://shorturl.at/0V4TU>